

Insect and vertebrate pests of deep water rice in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

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In 1984, 400,000 ha in 5 districts of 2 provinces was surveyed for insect and

Deep water rice area (dotted) and sites of pest survey in Vietnam, 1984.

vertebrate pests (see figure). Five farmers' fields in each district were surveyed at 3 wk after seed germination, middle of flooding (Aug), and from flowering to harvest time. The data were confirmed by farmer interviews and general observations.

The most serious pest from booting to soft dough stage is the yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas*, with a whitehead incidence of 4-10% (see table). The incidence of *Rattus argentiventer*, a serious vertebrate pest, depends on yearly flooding, with a high incidence in years of late and low flood.

Mus musculus homourus, another rodent species, causes damage in some areas. *R. argentiventer* and the mole cricket *Gryllotalpa africana* are serious pests at preemergence and early seedling stages because most deep water rice is direct seeded with ungerminated seeds.

Chemical control by treating soil or seeds at seeding is the main practice for pest management in deep water areas; later stages are seldom sprayed. Cultural practices such as fallow, stubble burning, and cultivation of mungbean and sesame are followed in some areas. *S*

Major insect and vertebrate pests of deep water rice in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam, 1984.

Pest species	Pest importance ^a		
	Preflooding	Flooding	After flowering
<i>Gryllotalpa africana</i>	++		
<i>Stenchaetothrips biformis</i>	+ - ++		
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	+		
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	+ - ++	+	
<i>Chilo</i> spp.	+		
<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i>	+	+	++
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	+	+	
<i>Scotinophara coarctata</i>	+	+	
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>	+	+	++
<i>Rattus argentiventer</i>	++	+	++

^a+ = minor, ++ = major.

Survival of adult *Nephotettix virescens* in test tube

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To screen for tungro virus (RTV) resistance in rice, the variety, whether it is susceptible to the vector, is not preferred, or has antibiosis, must be exposed to the vector for at least the minimum duration required for successful plant inoculation. Even when confined, the vector may avoid nonpreferred and resistant plants and may not initiate the sustained feeding necessary for RTV transmission.

On the other hand, prolonged desiccation and/or food deprivation may kill the vector. How long the RTV vector green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* can survive without food and water is not known.

We used 7-d-old TN1 rice seedlings as the food plant and caged newly emerged insects at the rate of 1 adult/test tube in 3 treatments: no water, no plant; water with no plant; water and plant. Each treatment was replicated twice with 40 insects/treatment. Surviving adults were counted at 6-h intervals the first day and at 24-h intervals subsequently.

When deprived of both food and water, 75% adults died within 6 h and all died within 24 h (see table). When

only water was provided, 71% adults survived the first 24 h and 37% survived up to 48 h. When both food and water were available, all adults survived at least 1 d, and 59% survived 7 d.

The results show that at least some individuals can survive for 1-2 d in test tubes without feeding on nonpreferred or resistant plants. Such plants could escape infection by insects placed inside the test tubes for inoculation feeding. *S*

Surviving *N. virescens* adults in food and water deprivation test.^a Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Treatment	Surviving insects (%) at indicated hours after confinement								
	6 h	12 h	24 h	48 h	72 h	96 h	120 h	144 h	168 h
No plant, no water	25	9	0						
Water with no plant	99	90	71	37	19	12	7	4	3
Water and plant	100	100	100	95	92	84	82	75	59

^aMeans of 2 replications.